

Finding ‘similar’ universities using ChatGPT. A large-scale comparison using ETER data

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It has recently been argued that ChatGPT might become a serious competitor to quantitative approaches to identify similar institutions for the purposes of comparing research performance in benchmarking studies. However, it is largely unknown how ChatGPT finds out ‘similar’ universities and whether results depend on the information provided by the user, and are stable over different queries. To address these questions, in this study, we resort to a sample of more than 1,000 universities included in the European Tertiary Education Register (ETER). We test different ChatGPT queries providing different levels of information on the focal university and we compare results with similarities computed from quantitative data in ETER. Preliminary results suggest that ChatGPT is able to identify some good peers, but the results strongly depend on the querying strategy and on the universities’ characteristics.

Keywords. Benchmarking; Higher Education Institutions; European Tertiary Education Register; ChatGPT, Generative Artificial Intelligence.

Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in benchmarking universities, particularly with respect to their research performance (Moed, et al 1985, van Raan 2013) as well as their efficiency (Daraio, Bonaccorsi and Simar 2015a). However, it is acknowledged that several characteristics of universities, such as different subject compositions, size, and institutional mission, significantly affect comparisons also when using so-called field- or size-normalized indicators (Bornmann, de Moya Anegón and Mutz 2013; Abramo and D’Angelo 2016). It has also been argued that “such differences between universities are reflected in university rankings and should be taken into account in the interpretation of these rankings” (Waltman, Wouters and van Eck 2017).

While advanced approaches have been introduced in order to compare research performance and/or efficiency on large sample by taking into account higher education institutions (HEIs) heterogeneity (Daraio, Bonaccorsi and Simar 2015b), methodologies for identifying peer institutions, i.e., institutions sufficiently similar to a focal one to allow for meaningful comparisons, have been much less developed. The few papers in the scientometrics literature are limited to individual case studies, but do not provide general approaches to identify peer institutions (Noyons, Moed and Luwel 1999 Carayol, Filliatreau and Lahatte 2012, Wang and Jeppsson 2022).

The fact that approaches to identify peers have been introduced by some rankings, such as the Scimago Institutional Ranking, witnesses a growing interest by users for peer identification. An interactive tool to identify similar institutions has also been developed by the U-MULTIRANK project (<https://benchmarking.umultirank.org/>; see also van Vught and Ziegele 2012), and more recently by the reference database on European higher education, i.e. the European Tertiary Education Register (ETER, Lepori, et al 2023).

The goal of this study is to explore another potential direction for peer identification, i.e., the use of generative artificial intelligence (AI), and more specifically of ChatGPT to identify potential peer institutions to a focal institution. Several scholars suggested that generative AI,

and specifically ChatGPT, has a potential for science studies as it allows combining different sources of information and exploiting machine learning to develop categorizations. However, the extent to which results are reliable is widely debated and, notably, the tool lack of transparency on how results are generated (Sandnes 2024).

In first explorations of the use of ChatGPT for identifying peer universities, Bornmann and Lepori (2024) showed that, if a suitable querying strategy is adopted, ChatGPT might be able to provide meaningful results. They also remarked that ChatGPT has the potential for overcoming data limitations of database-based tools and it has attractive features for users, such as simplicity and interactivity (Rahman and Watanobe 2023). Hence, even if the quality of results might be lower than database-driven tools, it might become a serious competitor for some type of users.

In this perspective, it is important to provide a systematic evaluation of the identification of peer universities by ChatGPT and the extent to which its quality depends on the specific querying strategy (such as the amount of information provided by the user) and on the universities' characteristics, such as their degree of visibility and size. The goal of this study is therefore to systematically assess the quality of peer identification by ChatGPT on a large sample of universities for which we have quantitative data from ETER – focusing specifically on identifying similar peers in terms of three core characteristics of HEIs, i.e., their size, their subject composition, and their research output.

We use ETER information in this study on two grounds: first, to test the extent to which peer identification by ChatGPT improves when providing some information on the focal university, for example whether it is large or focused on specific subjects. Second, to quantitatively measure to which extent the peers identified by ChatGPT are indeed the most similar universities in the ETER database when computing similarities using quantitative indicators, such as the number of academic personnel for institutional size.

Data and methods

Data Sources

We derive our data from ETER (Lepori, et al 2023). ETER is the reference database on European HEIs established by the European Commission. ETER provides a wealth of data at the institutional level for more than 3,000 HEIs in 41 European countries (EU-27, UK, European Economic Area/European free Trade Agreement countries, as well as candidate and potential EU candidate countries) for the years 2011 to 2021. The data include descriptive information, location, numbers of students and graduates (with various breakdowns), numbers of PhD students and graduates, as well as data on personnel and finances (revenues and expenditures). ETER data are provided by national statistical authorities from the same data collection used for EUROSTAT educational statistics (UOE 2013). Data are subject to extensive consistency and quality checks. The dataset is extensively annotated for previously detected data problems, which could not be resolved with data providers. Coverage of tertiary education as compared with EUROSTAT ranges between 90% and 95% of the enrolled students in most countries. ETER's coverage extends well beyond universities, to comprise also colleges and other HEIs with limited or no research activity (Lepori 2022). However, for this study, we limit our sample to PhD-awarding institutions ('universities') since our focus is on identifying peers for comparing research performance: We use ETER data for the year 2022, and our sample includes 1,393 universities.

ETER data have been enriched with publication data provided through the RISIS project (<https://www.risis2.eu>); data are based on the Web of Science (WoS, Clarivate) and computed with the same methodology as in the Leiden ranking (Waltman, et al 2012). Overall, 1,329

universities in our sample have been identified in the WoS, the remaining ones have been attributed a publication number of null.

Variables and classifications

For identifying peers, we take into account three characteristics of universities:

- University size as measured by total academic personnel in Full-Time Equivalents (FTE). Size is a fundamental characteristic of universities, which is known to have an impact on research performance and position in international rankings (Lepori, Geuna and Mira 2019). We prefer personnel over financial data due to better availability and comparability in ETER (Lepori, Bornmann and de Moya Anegón 2023).
- Subject composition as measured by the number of students by Field of Education and Training, i.e., the standard classification of educational fields in official statistics. Subject composition is known to strongly impact research performance and to affect bibliometric measures even size- and field-normalized (Bornmann, de Moya Anegón and Mutz 2013).
- Given the strong impact of the presence of a university hospital on observed research performance of a university, we also control for this characteristic, following the approach adopted by the Leiden ranking (Elizondo, Calero-Medina and Visser 2022).
- The research intensity of the university, measured by the number of publications divided by academic personnel in FTEs, as the goal is to identify peers with similar research intensity.

Table 1. Variables used in the analysis and descriptive statistics.

Variable	Definition	N	Min	P25	P50	P75	P90	Max	Mean
Size	Academic personnel in FTEs	1159	0	205	512	1237	2271	7325	913
Subject concentration	Herfindahl index of students by Fields of Education and Training	933	0.12	0.17	0.26	0.58	0.95	1	0.40
University hospital	1= associated university hospital, 0= no hospital	1393	0	0	0	1	1	1	0.26
Research intensity	Total publications/ academic personnel FTE	1155	0	0.34	0.88	1.82	2.88	104.7	1.31

For the purpose of querying ChatGPT, we generate from these data categorical indicators such as ‘large’, ‘small’, etc. The definition of the categories is driven by the higher education literature and by data exploration and analysis of descriptive statistics (Table 1).

- *Size*. The distribution of university size is nearly lognormal, with a large number of ‘small’ universities and few ‘large’ universities. Based on the percentiles, we define *small* universities as below p25, *medium* universities as below p50, *large* universities as below p90 and *very large* universities as exceeding p90.
- *Subject composition*. We follow the distinction established in the literature between generalist, focused and specialist HEIs, which we operationalize through the Herfindahl index of the distribution of students by field: *generalist* below 0.25, *focused* between 0.25 and 0.65 and *specialist* above 0.65. With these thresholds, generalist HEIs cannot have most of their students in a single field, while specialist HEIs must enrol at least 80% of the students in a single field.
- To better characterize *specialized universities*, we also add information on the fields in which more than a quarter of the total students are enrolled.

- We characterize the presence of a *university hospital* using the corresponding dummy variable in ETER. As shown by descriptive statistics, nearly one-quarter of the universities in our sample has an associated university hospital.
- *Research intensity*. Since the distribution of research intensity is very skewed, we adopt asymmetric categories as follows: low intensity below p25, medium intensity below p50, high intensity below p90, and very high intensity above p90.

This classification yields therefore $4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 4 = 96$ cells (disregarding the indication of the subject fields). Since the variables adopted are correlated, some cells are empty or with low number of cases – for instance, there are no specialized universities of very large size.

Querying ChatGPT

Interaction with ChatGPT and similar conversational large language models (LLMs) involves a structured exchange of messages identified by system, user and assistant (the AI itself) roles. The interaction is typically initiated by a system prompt that sets the stage for the conversation, e.g., by providing contextual information and instructions for the assistant’s responses, followed by user prompts that contain specific requests or queries. The conversational AI processes each of the user prompts and generates responses from the assistant, which may include direct answers or questions for further clarification (Burger, et al 2023; OpenAI 2023).

Prompt engineering is a set of methods and practices for designing and refining the input provided to an LLM for a given task, with the goal of ensuring specific qualities and quantities of the output produced (Giray, 2023; White *et al.*, 2023). Prompt engineering techniques include providing detailed and step-by-step instructions, supplying examples and reference data, instructing the LLM to adopt a specific persona, and systematically testing changes (OpenAI, 2023; White *et al.*, 2023).

We considered three different approaches to formulate the prompt for identifying the HEIs most similar to a focal institution. The first approach is fairly straightforward, as it simply includes the name of the institution in both English and its local language in the prompt, along with instructions for generating responses in a machine-readable form, as noted in Table 2. This variant emulates the approach taken by a casual user of ChatGPT. In this case, ChatGPT was given the freedom to determine what constitutes similarity between institutions, except for the focus on comparing the research performance of universities.

The second approach builds on the first approach but includes a concise description of the specific dimensions to consider when identifying similar institutions, as might be expected of a user with a moderate knowledge of prompt engineering (Table 2).

Table 2. Variants of prompts used. Directives to the LLM for generating machine-readable responses are omitted.

Prompt	System or user prompt	Prompt example
Simple (query 1)	System prompt	My aim is to identify universities similar to a given university in order to compare their research performance. Prioritize recent information.
	User prompt	Please list the 5 universities in Europe that are most similar to Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam (also known as: Erasmus University Rotterdam) in terms of research performance.
Intermediate (query 2)	System prompt	My aim is to identify universities similar to a given university in order to compare their research performance. Universities should be similar in terms of: a) their size as measured by academic personnel,

		b) the main educational subjects covered, c) their degree of subject concentration, d) their degree of research intensity as measured by the number of publications relative to size, e) whether they are formally associated with a university hospital. Prioritize recent information, aiming for accuracy and relevance.
	User prompt	According to the information I have, Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam (also known as: Erasmus University Rotterdam) can be characterized as of large in size, addressing mainly these subjects: social sciences, business administration and law, focused in terms of subject concentration, and having a very high research intensity. Moreover, Erasmus University Rotterdam is associated with a university hospital. Given this information, please list the 5 most similar universities in Europe.

We also tried a third and most complex approach that involves a detailed explanation of these dimensions and their respective categorization as defined in the ETER database. This option was designed to force the LLM to build its responses progressively. After careful consideration, we have decided to discard this third approach, as it was found to deviate significantly from the expected behaviour of an average user of ChatGPT and to assume knowledge of the ETER database.

To enable iterative experimentation while minimizing repetitive tasks, we built a test environment based on a program written in the Python programming language. The environment takes as input a list of HEIs, a system and user prompt, and the query parameters, such as the specific LLM to be consulted. The program iteratively builds the queries and interrogates the LLM by accessing the OpenAI application programming interface (API). The program then collects the results returned by ChatGPT and stores them in a machine-readable table for subsequent analysis.

Analyzing results

Given the wide coverage of the ETER database, we expect that almost all peers identified by ChatGPT are also present in the ETER database. This allows for a systematic comparison of the peers' characteristics with those of the focal university by using the ETER data.

More specifically, we perform the following tests:

- Whether the peers identified by ChatGPT are classified in the same way as the focal university using the dimensions and categories defined above. This is informative about the ability of ChatGPT to find 'reasonable' peers according to the defined dimensions.
- Whether there are other universities in the ETER database more similar to the focal university as the peers identified by ChatGPT. To this aim, we construct a composite similarity index according to the identified dimensions (for example, using Euclidean distance). This is informative of whether ChatGPT is able to identify the best possible peers (as related to proposed dimensions).
- The extent to which the quality of ChatGPT results improves by providing more information on the focal university, as derived from the ETER database.
- To what extent the results depend on the characteristics of the focal university, for example, whether ChatGPT provides better results for large and well-known institutions or whether results are less precise for specific types of institutions.

Preliminary results

As a preliminary step, we conduct a query on fifteen universities in different European countries, selected to be rather diverse in terms of subject orientation, but all of them being rather large and research oriented. As these universities are more visible, for example in international rankings, we expect results to be fairly more precise than with the whole ETER sample. We employ query (2), which already includes information on the focal university. A similar test using query (1) yield a very different set of peers (only 23 out of 75 peers are the same), therefore confirming the expectation that providing specific information significantly affects results. Table 3 provides an overview of the test cases, the peers proposed by ChatGPT and an assessment of the fit with the criteria.

Table 3. Test cases and correspondence with the ETER categories.

Focal university	ChatGPT Peers	Size	Hospital	Research intensity	Specialization	Main subject
Polytechnic of Milan	Federal Institute of Technology Zurich, Technical University of Munich, Delft University of Technology, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Imperial College London	4/5	2/5	3/5	1/5	5/5
Erasmus University Rotterdam	University of Zurich, University of Mannheim, Università Bocconi, Karolinska Institutet, London School of Economics and Political Science	3/5	2/5	3/5	2/5	3/5
Università della Svizzera italiana	Università Bocconi, University of Sankt Gallen, Paris Institute of political studies, Tilburg University, The University of Essex	2/5	5/5	3/5	0/5	1/5
University of Göttingen	Heidelberg University, University of Munich, The University of Cambridge, The University of Oxford	5/5	5/5	2/5	5/5	-
Humboldt University Berlin	University of Vienna, University of Amsterdam, University of Warsaw, The University of Cambridge, The University of Oxford	5/5	2/5	3/5	4/5	-
Université de Fribourg	University of Mannheim, University of Copenhagen, University of Strasbourg, Maastricht University, The University of Warwick	1/5	4/5	3/5	2/5	3/5
University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague	Politecnico di Milano, Federal Institute of Technology Zurich, Technical University of Munich, Delft University of Technology, KTH Royal Institute of Technology	2/5	3/5	2/5	2/5	5/5
Tampere University	Aachen University, Technical University of Denmark, Aalto University, Delft University of Technology, KTH Royal Institute of Technology	1/5	2/5	4/5	0/5	5/5
The University of Bath	The University of Exeter, The University of Lancaster, The University of Surrey, The University of Warwick, The University of York	4/5	3/5	3/5	-	-

Focal university	ChatGPT Peers	Size	Hospital	Research intensity	Specialization	Main subject
University of Economics, Prague	Vienna University of Economics and Business, London School of Economics and Political Science, Università Bocconi, Copenhagen Business School, Stockholm School of Economics	3/5	5/5	3/5	1/5	4/5
University of Tartu	Ghent University, University of Helsinki, University of Copenhagen, University of Groningen, Uppsala University	0/5	5/5	2/5	5/5	-
Technical University of Madrid	Politecnico di Milano, Federal Institute of Technology Zurich, Technical University of Munich, Delft University of Technology, KTH Royal Institute of Technology	3/5	4/5	2/5	2/5	5/5
University of Patras	Politecnico di Milano, Federal Institute of Technology Zurich, Technical University of Munich, Delft University of Technology, Imperial College London	1/5	2/5	3/5	1/5	5/5
University of Palermo	Leipzig University, University of Barcelona, University of Strasbourg, University of Padova, The University of Manchester	0/5	5/5	2/5	3/5	-
University of Latvia	University of Tartu, Charles University, University of Helsinki, Vilnius University, University of Warsaw	2/5	4/5	5/5	4/5	-

Despite its preliminary and partial nature, this test already displays some interesting patterns. In terms of the criteria (e.g., size), ChatGPT provides quite good results in terms of the level of research intensity. It is able to identify fairly well situations where there is a university hospital. However, the program has issues to deal with complex situations like Berlin, where Humboldt University is formally associated with La Charité hospital, but the whole medical education is in the hospital. In terms of subject specialization, ChatGPT seems to be able to identify good peers for broad generalist universities, and for the very specialized universities, such as technical universities. However, for universities whose profile is focused on few domains, identification is more problematic, as shown by the case of Erasmus University Rotterdam, a business school including also a medical college. Results concerning size are more mixed.

A closer look to the ChatGPT textual answers shows that some differences between the delivered universities are acknowledged. For example, when indicating Karolinska (a medical school) as a peer for the University of Rotterdam (a university with a strong focus on business, but including a medical school), ChatGPT provides the following information:

Although primarily focused on health sciences, it shares a very high research intensity and is associated with a university hospital. The focus on a specific subject area is high, but the main educational subjects differ, affecting the similarity score.

And when indicating SciencePo (a specialized French University in political sciences) as a peer for Università della Svizzera italiana (a broad university with strong social sciences alongside informatics and a medical school), ChatGPT comes up with the following remark:

Sciences Po is renowned for its focus on social sciences, similar to Università della Svizzera italiana, though it is slightly more specialized in political science and international relations. Both are of medium size, have high research intensity, and are not affiliated with a university hospital. The strong international orientation and research

output in social sciences at Sciences Po align closely with the profile of Università della Svizzera italiana.

This suggests that what is at stake is not the availability of information, but how this information is valued. More specifically, ChatGPT may not fully weight the core importance of disciplinary structures in academia and how seemingly small differences in that respect might be key for the user. Another remark concerns why ChatGPT does not find better peers in these cases: one reason might be the lack of information beyond the most visible universities in Europe. For instance, while peers for Polytechnic of Milan are all reasonable, we notice that the most similar (but not as visible as others) institution in the country, i.e., Polytechnic of Turin, was not identified.

Discussion and conclusions

We have suggested that ChatGPT might become an important competitor to quantitative approaches to identifying peer universities because of attractive features to users, such as ease of access and interactivity. However, by its design, ChatGPT is a black box and it is not known what kind of inferences it makes. Accordingly, we argued that it is important to systematically assess its performance in identifying similar institutions by comparing with a gold standard represented, as of Europe, by ETER.

Namely, by comparing with ETER data, we seek to understand how ChatGPT interprets a complex construct such universities' similarity and/or diversity and on how this is affected by the user providing more precise information on the concept, but also on the focal institutions. Our preliminary results suggest that indeed providing more information strongly affects ChatGPT's searching behavior and results. The examples we have provided seem to suggest that the results are more precise for some types of institutions, unsurprisingly those that are more distinctive such as technical universities. Overall, the supervised query we employed seems to provide many reasonable peers, alongside some unlikely matches.

In the next steps of our project, the empirical results will be analyzed more systematically on the ETER whole sample, outcomes of different query strategies will be compared and, finally, the stability of results when repeating queries will be examined. This will provide a more precise understanding of ChatGPT's performance in identifying similar universities, and might also allow for suggesting sensible querying strategies that, while providing sufficient information, still leaves to the model enough room for proposing interesting peers.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: BL, LB.

Formal analysis: BL.

Investigation: MG

Methodology: BL.

Validation: BL, MG.

Writing – original draft: BL, MG.

Writing – review & editing: BL, LB.

Competing interests

We have no competing interests to declare.

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